

Studies in Angular Furocoumarins: Part III. Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of Allopsoralene Derivatives

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Ultraviolet absorption spectra of allopsoralene derivatives measured in the region 200-360 $m\mu$ show that substitution of hydrogen at 4-position by phenyl group is accompanied by bathochromic shift. Reduction of furan ring causes bathochromic effect of one of the bands (B_b). The absorption spectra of angular furocoumarins viz. isopsoralenes and allopsoralenes compare fairly well with that of phenanthrene and that of psoralene is comparable with the absorption spectra of anthracene.

The best known physiological activity of furocoumarins is their skin photosensitizing property. A relationship between structure and photodynamic activity of furocoumarins has been observed by Musajo *et al*¹ who claim that angular furocoumarins are less active than the linear ones. The above fact together with the view held by Pathak and Fellman² that there is correlation between light absorption and photosensitizing activity led us to study the U.V. absorption patterns of the three possible types I, II and III of furocoumarins based on resorcinol, typical members of the first two type being psoralene and isopsoralene both occurring in nature.

Fig-1

Study of U.V. absorption spectra of substituted psoralenes and isopsoralenes have already been reported by us^{3,4}. We are now reporting the study of U.V. absorption spectra of the third type of furocoumarin III. A synthetic compound -7-methoxy derivative of the parent structure III has been assigned the name allobergapten by

1. L. Musajo and G. Rodighiero, *Experientia*, 1962, **18**, 153.
2. M. A. Pathak and J. H. Fellman, *Nature*, 1960, **185**, 382.
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Spath⁵ and hence III which has not been isolated from natural sources nor synthesised is designated allopsoralene. The compounds synthesised and studied by us are furo-8-ethyl-5', 4' : 5, 6-coumarin derivatives or derivatives of allopsoralene, substituted at 3 and 4-positions by alkyl and aryl groups.

For the synthesis of allopsoralenes VII, we have employed 5-ethyl-6-hydroxycoumaran⁶ IV as starting material, which was synthesised by Hoesch condensation of 6-hydroxycoumaran and acetonitrile, and reduction of the resulting ketone with Zink amalgam and concentrated hydrochloric acid. IV was condensed with appropriate β -keto esters V followed by dehydrogenation of the resulting dihydro-allopsoralenes VI with 10% palladium-carbon in refluxing diphenyl ether.

- (a) $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = H$
 (b) $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$
 V (c) $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = Et$
 (d) $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = nBu$
 VI (e) $R_1R_2 = -CH_2CH_2CH_2-$
 (f) $R_1R_2 = -CH_2CH_2CH_2CH_2-$
 (g) $R_1 = C_6H_5, R_2 = H$
 VII (h) $R_1 = C_6H_5, R_2 = CH_3$

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected. The compounds were repeatedly crystallized from the solvents until sharp and constant melting points and single spot on TLC were obtained.

Absorption was measured with a Hilger Automatic Recording Spectrophotometer using ethanol as solvent at a concentration of 4-5 mg/litre in the region 200-360 $m\mu$.

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6. J. S. H. Davies, P. A. McCrea, W. L. Norris and G. R. Ramage, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3206.

Preparation of derivatives of Furo-2', 3'-dihydro-8-ethyl-5',4' : 5,6-coumarin (VI) : A mixture of 5-ethyl-6-hydroxy benzofuran IV (0.010 mole), appropriate β -keto ester (0.010 mole) was treated with concentrated sulfuric acid (4 ml) maintaining the temperature below 5°. After keeping at room temperature for 18 hours the solution was poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid was filtered off and the residue was washed with 5% caustic soda and water, purified by vacuum sublimation (200°/1 mm) and crystallised from appropriate solvent.

Different furodihydrocoumarins having general formula VI (all new compounds) prepared following the above procedure, along with their physical properties and analytical data are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

Derivatives of Furo-2', 3'-dihydro-8-ethyl-5', 4' : 5, 6-coumarin

Compound No. VI	M.P. °C.	Cryst. solvent	Yield%	Formula	Analysis			
					Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
(a)	113	Ethyl acetate	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃	73.02	73.14	6.13	6.31
(b)	131	Methanol	82	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₃	73.75	73.49	6.60	6.90
(c)	121	Methanol	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₃	74.39	74.18	7.02	7.01
(d)	94	Methanol (dil)	26	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₃	75.49	75.61	7.74	7.48
(e)	142	Methanol	74	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃	74.98	74.75	6.29	6.01
(f)	140	Methanol	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₃	75.53	75.29	6.71	6.65
(g)	155	Methanol	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃	78.06	77.78	5.52	5.24
(h)	185	Methanol	32	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₃	78.41	78.78	5.92	6.06

Preparation of derivatives of Furo-8-ethyl-5', 4' : 5,6-coumarin (VII) : A mixture of VI (0.4 g), 10% Pd/C (0.2 g) and diphenyl oxide (16 ml) was heated under reflux for 6 hrs. Catalyst was removed from the hot solution by filtration and the filtrate after removal of solvent by distillation under reduced pressure gave a solid which on purification by vacuum sublimation at 200°/1.0 mm. and crystallisation from appropriate solvent yielded the pure material.

Different furocoumarins prepared by this method having general formula VII (all new compounds) along with their physical properties and analytical data are listed in Table II.

TABLE II

Derivatives of Furo-8-ethyl-5', 4' : 5, 6-coumarin

Compound No. VII	M.P. °C.	Cryst. solvent	Yield%	Formula	Analysis			
					Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
(a)	144	Ethyl acetate	90	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃	73.67	73.82	5.30	5.51
(b)	152	Methanol	85	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃	74.36	74.25	5.83	5.75
(c)	105	Methanol (dil)	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃	74.98	75.14	6.20	6.54
(e)	163	Pet-ether	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃	75.57	75.73	5.55	5.67
(f)	121	Methanol	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃	76.10	76.35	6.01	5.83
(g)	173	Methanol	90	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₃	78.60	78.85	4.85	5.09

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Four types of absorption curves have been observed, a typical member of each type has been presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3

Ultraviolet absorption spectra of furo-8-ethyl-4-methyl-5', 4' : 5, 6-coumarin VII(a)—furo-2', 3'-dihydro-8-ethyl-4-methyl-5', 4' : 5, 6-coumarin VI(a)—□—□—; furo-8-ethyl-4-phenyl-5', 4' : 5, 6-coumarin VII(g)—Δ—Δ—; furo-2', 3'-dihydro-8-ethyl-4-phenyl-5', 4' : 5, 6-coumarin VI(g)—O—O—.

Table III is the summary of important features from the absorption spectra.

TABLE III

Ultraviolet absorption data of the derivatives of 8-ethylallopsoralene

Compound	$\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ)					
VII(a)	221		244	260 ^a	299	346
	4.30		4.47		4.20	3.56
VII(b)	221		245	261 ^a	300	348
	4.30		4.38		4.12	3.48
VII(c)	221		245	262 ^a	300	350
	4.13		4.31		4.11	3.48
VII(e)	222		246	262 ^a	300	350
	4.28		4.39		4.15	3.48
VII(f)		235	241	274	284	312 ^b
		4.89	4.87	4.47	4.45	4.23
VII(g)	224		248	264 ^a	308	350
	4.35		4.43		4.12	3.64
VI(a)	219	229 ^a		263	302	342
	4.12	4.01		4.11	4.10	3.50
VI(b)	221	233 ^a		263	300	345
	4.27	4.12		4.19	4.16	3.55
VI(c)	219	233 ^a		263	300	350
	4.24	3.92		4.09	4.11	3.41
VI(d)	221	233 ^a		264	302	350
	4.32	4.08		4.18	4.17	3.36
VI(e)	221	233 ^a		262	302	350
	4.47	4.26		4.25	4.20	3.55
VI(f)	221	231 ^a		264	300	344
	4.25	4.07		4.18	4.13	3.54
VI(g)	221	233 ^a		267	310	350
	4.45	4.29		4.25	4.10	3.48
VI(h)	221	235		266	308	350
	4.36	4.03		4.15	4.07	3.50

a. Inflection, b. Shoulder.

Significant points of interest are as follows. Substitution at 3,4-positions of hydrogen by alkyl groups, of 8-ethyl furo-5', 4' : 5,6-coumarin does not produce any significant change in absorption pattern. Substitution by cyclohexeno group causes partial merger of bands at 220 ± 1 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 4.20 ± 0.1) and 245 ± 1 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 4.40 ± 0.1) resulting into a twin peak at 235 and 241 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 4.9). Also instead of inflection at 261 $m\mu$ and band at 300 $m\mu$, peaks at 274 and 284 $m\mu$ and shoulder at 298–312 $m\mu$ are observed.

Substitution by phenyl group causes bathochromic shift of all the bands with accompanying increase in intensity of absorption.

Reduction of the furano ring causes a red shift of the band at $245\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.40) to $263 \pm 1\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.1).

The spectra of angular furocoumarins resemble very closely those of the corresponding angular tricyclic aromatic molecule phenanthrene corroborating the idea put forward by Badger and Christie⁷ that there is a fundamental similarity between the spectra of heterocyclic compounds and those of related benzenoid molecules.

Three groups of bands characteristic of aromatic $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition (L_b , L_a , B_b)^{*} as observed in case of phenanthrene⁸ at $350\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 2.54), $293\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.20), $251\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.81) respectively are found also in case of allopsoralenes at $345\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.48), $300\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.18) and $245\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.47) respectively. The L_b band is considerably stronger, the L_a band is slightly red shifted, the B_b is blue shifted and little weakened. A band (C_b) at $212\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.4) attributed to the feature that phenanthrene molecule has no centre of symmetry⁹ is observed here also at $221\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.30).

It is interesting to note that in the case of isopsoralene⁴ the L_a and L_b bands have merged to give rise to a broad band at $300\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.01), but the B_b ($248\text{ m}\mu$; $\log \epsilon$ 4.40) and C_b ($210\text{ m}\mu$; $\log \epsilon$ 4.26) bands are present at the expected positions.

Whereas in anthracene¹⁰ the L_b band has disappeared and L_a band is shifted to $378\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.93) bathochromically, in psoralene³ both the bands are resolved distinctly at $328\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.28 weak) and $292\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.04 stronger) respectively. B_b band of anthracene ($256\text{ m}\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 5.26) appears at $245\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.39) in psoralene.

Comparison of the spectra of the furocoumarins and the corresponding dihydrofurocoumarins reveals the following features: 1) the L_a band is weakened and the L_b band has become stronger in the reduced compounds of the type I, whereas in the case of reduced compounds of the type II the L_a - L_b band has bathochromically shifted with slight intensification and in cases of those of type III no such change of pattern of L_a and L_b bands is observable on reduction. 2) The B_b bands of the reduced compounds of type I and III, are weakened and shifted bathochromically, whereas those of type II appears as much weaker twin peak and 3) the C_b bands of compounds of type I which seem to be below our region of measurement appear at $225\text{ m}\mu$ due to a red shift³ in the case of dihydrocompounds.

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* Notations associated with transverse and longitudinal polarisation of aromatic molecules as introduced by Platt⁸.

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